

CORRELATION OF SERUM FERRITIN WITH SEVERITY OF NON-ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER (NAFLD) PATIENT

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17875549>

Keywords

Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease, NAFLD, Non-Alcoholic Steatohepatitis, NASH, Serum Ferritin, Biomarker, Iron Metabolism, Hepatic Steatosis, Liver Function Tests, Disease Severity, Ultrasound Grading, Non-Invasive Assessment, Pakistan, South Asia

Article History

Received: 19 October 2025

Accepted: 24 November 2025

Published: 09 December 2025

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Abstract

Background: Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is now the most common chronic liver condition worldwide and its progression from simple steatosis to its severe stage NASH, then came fibrosis and cirrhosis. For its diagnosis liver biopsy is the gold standard to check the severity but its invasive and too much costly. serum ferritin work as acute phase reactant and iron stores. and also serve as a noninvasive biomarker for NAFLD but data from south Asian population including Pakistan are very limited

Objective: To evaluate the correlation between serum ferritin levels and NAFLD severity in Pakistani patients and assess its potential as a non-invasive biomarker.

Method: A cross-sectional study was conducted in Nawaz shareef social security hospital Lahore it includes 130 patients with confirm diagnosed NAFLD through ultrasound. the patient was dividing into 3 grades. Grade 1 consist of 42 patients and grade 2 consist of 55 patients while grade 3 have 33 patient and demographic data like age and gender, lft and serum ferritin was recorded. the statistical analysis is done using spss27 including spearman correlation

Results: Mean age was 46.16 ± 9.33 years; 56.2% male. Grade 2 was the most common (42.3%). Serum ferritin is strongly correlated with NAFLD severity ($r_s = 0.935$, $p < 0.001$), rising from 216.24 ± 8.93 ng/mL (Grade 1) to 396.00 ± 25.22 ng/mL (Grade 3), an 83% increase. Differences between grades were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). The correlation is stronger than most Western reports, consistent with regional trends.

Conclusion: In this research Serum ferritin show a very strong relation with the severity of NAFLD in Pakistani patient and is a valuable non-invasive biomarker. Its routine measurement can aid risk stratification and monitoring, offering a

low-cost, accessible alternative to invasive procedures. And next the longitudinal studies are needed to validate cutoff values and prognostic utility.

INTRODUCTION

Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is also known as metabolic dysfunction-associated liver disease (MASLD). It is a condition that is characterized by the collection of fat on liver cells over 5% while the patient has no alcohol history. The NAFLD includes the number of liver problems which are linked to each other, like nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH), and liver cirrhosis, and liver fibrosis. Nonalcoholic fatty liver disease is one of the most common causes of chronic liver disease world wide but still we do not have advance information about this disease like is this due to fat in the liver or mild inflammation in the liver. but when this disease increases their effect and starts damaging the liver cells, they become nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH).¹

Spectrum of NAFLD

Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease shows multiple spectra of liver pathology that vary from simple fat accumulation on liver cells to most worsen stage cirrhosis to understand this disease spectrum following is the step by step explain nation of different stages of this disease

Simple Hepatic Steatosis

It is the earliest stage of NAFLD called simple hepatic steatosis .in this stage fat deposition is more than 5 % of liver cell but it does not cause any inflammation or cell damage. in this stage liver look normal under the microscope and patient are also feel nothing.²

Non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH)

The very next stage after simple steatosis is non-alcoholic steatohepatitis commonly known as NASH which is more serious condition then first one. NASH is important because it represent a point where liver is start damaging and scarred occur on it.³

Fibrosis

If NASH remain untreated, they became more worsen condition call fibrosis. in this condition scar tissue start replacing with liver tissue usually doctors grade this condition into 4 steps F0 to F4 which then call cirrhosis.⁴

Cirrhosis The final stage of the disease where a large number of scars hares been formed and due to this liver is not preforming properly anymore. the patient at this stage can develop life threatening complications like fluid in abdomen, bleeding from swollen veins in the esophagus etc.⁵

Figure 1: spectrum of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD)

Progression of disease

The severity of NAFLD varies among patients. Researches show that approximately one-third of patient had worsen liver scars over time while 43% remain stable and 22% actually improve. this speed or recover depend heavily on which stage of disease patent is suffering from. Those with simple fatty liver

progress slowly, approximately take 14 years to advance stage like simple to fibrosis.⁶

The time line from navel from simplest stage to more worsen stage spans many years approximately 20% of patient with fatty liver develop within 3 to 7 years while these numbers indicate that all the patients reach end stage.⁷

Figure.2 Disease Progression Flowchart

Mechanism of progression.

Non-alcoholic fatty liver progress involves multiple harmful process that happened continuously called multiple hit hypothesis the initial fat deposition makes the liver vulnerable to injuries including oxidative stress from damaged mitochondria, stress in protein making machinery.⁸

These process continuously wok and damage the liver cell, trigger inflammation and also activate lever stellate cells that produce scars on liver .to understand this progression patterns are important for the identification of high-risk patients and developing treatments that stops and reverse disease progression.⁹

Pathophysiology of NAFLD

cycle for liver damage some of the explain below Insulin resistance and lipid accumulation

Insulin resistance

The insulin resistance is known as the fundamental defect which cause fatty liver. in healthy patients' insulin regulates glucose uptake, and suppressed the liver glucose production and it also control the breakdown of fat. In insulin resistance cell are not responsive to insulin signals and forcing the pancreas that they have to produce more and more insulin. this affects three critical organs muscle, liver, and fat tissues .in muscles the glucose uptake becomes impaired but in liver glucose production unchecked. in NAFLD insulin resistance in fat tissue cause uncontrolled breakdown of stored fat which releases a flood of fatty acid into the bloodstream that accumulates in the liver.¹⁰Liver receives fatty acid from three sources like blood stream, release from its own fat stores and produce new fat through de novo

lipogenesis. this fat liver burned or stored as triglycerides or exported but when it does not do any action, they start deposition on liver cell with cause fatty liver.¹¹

Oxidative stress and mitochondrial dysfunction

Mitochondria are the power house it is responsible for the burning of fatty acid that is deposited on liver to generate energy .in NAFLD there is excess of fatty acid that force it to work even harder due to this mitochondria overwhelmed and start leaking electrons , generates dangerous reactive oxygen species such as superoxide and hydroxyl radicals these molecules damage mitochondrial DNA and also oxidize membrane and impair the repertory chain, which create vicious cycle and then mitochondria produce even more harmful oxidants.¹²This stat of oxidative stress is dangerous for NAFLD progression to NASH. the oxygen specie reacts with lipid present on membranes through lipid peroxidation and damage the protein and DNA and activate inflammatory signaling pathways. ATP production decreases and the capacity for fatty acid oxidation declines.¹³

From inflammation to fibrosis

The pathogenic mechanism in hepatocyte injury and death when liver cell die that release specific signals that activates hepatic cells. these cells transform into collagen producing myofibroblasts, leading to progressive accumulation of scar tissue. They continuous their cycle of cell injury and inflammation and stellate cels activation cause fibrosis that initially look around cells but after some time connects into bands bridging that deferrers' liver structure it this is untreated, they would lead to cirrhosis where scars tissue completely distorts the liver normal architecture.¹⁴

SERUM FERRITIN AS A BIOMARKER NAFLD

The search for noninvasive marker to measure the NAFLKD severity had led the researches to examine serum ferritin as a potential tool. They check serum ferritin because of its inflammatory marker property to understand this explanation is below

Serum ferritin

Ferritin is the iron storage protein synthesized by the liver. but ferritin also have the function as an acute phase reactant means its production will increase in response of inflammation, infection or tissue injury, when the body experience inflammatory stress immune cell release cytokines that stimulate liver to produce more ferritin as a defense mechanism.¹⁵

Ferritin in NAFLD

Liver serves as the primary site for iron storage and ferritin synthesis. in NAFLD patients approximately 60 to 70 percent have elevated ferritin level. but only minor actually have significant hepatic iron accumulation when it is directly measured. this shows that there are many other conditions where we can form elevated serum ferritin levels beyond iron storage.¹⁶Damaged hepatocytes will leak ferritin directly into circulation. Systemic inflammation characteristic of NAFLD and metabolic syndrome stimulates ferritin production as an acute phase response. Insulin resistance affects iron metabolism through complex hormonal pathways. Additionally, some patients do have true hepatic iron accumulation which further increases ferritin synthesis.¹⁷

FERRITIN as a marker of disease severity

Many studies have shown that there is a relation with ferritin levels with NAFLD. patient have 1.5 times upper limit of normal ferritin level in degrees of steatosis, more inflammation, worse lever cell and more advance fibrosis. Increase ferritin is an independent predictor of advance hepatic fibrosis even after accounting for factors like age, body mass index, and diabetes status.¹⁸Ferritin levels increase progressively as fibrosis worsen from F0-F3 though interestingly, levels may decrease in cirrhotic patients, possibly reflecting decreased synthetic capacity of the severely damaged liver.¹⁹Long-term follow-up studies show that elevated ferritin not only correlates with histologic severity but also predicts clinical outcomes, with patients having elevated ferritin at baseline showing significantly increased mortality rates over time.²⁰

Currently the only best way to determine that how sever the NAFLD is through biopsy where a needle is used into the liver to obtain a small tissue sample for examination under a microscope but it is an invasive

procedure and also not available in all hospitals and healthcare settings .and also the small tissue obtain may not accurately represent the entire liver due to sampling variable and patient are understandably reluctant to undergo biopsies to monitor disease progression over time Given that NAFLD affects almost 30% of the world population, there is an urgent need for simple, non-invasive blood tests that can help doctors identify which patients have severe disease and are at high risk for complications.²¹

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study Design:

This was a cross-sectional study

STUDY SETTING

The study was conducted Nawaz shareef social security teaching hospital Lahore

Study duration

This study was completed in four months from august 2025 to November 2025 after the approval of synopsis.

Sample Size

A sample size of 130 patients was included for study.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria:

Inclusion criteria will be:

- Adults aged 18 years upto78 year

- Confirmed diagnosis of NAFLD through imaging.
- Ability to provide informed consent.
- Both male and female patients.

Exclusion criteria will include:

- Significant alcohol consumption.
- Presence of other liver diseases such as viral hepatitis or autoimmune hepatitis.
- Other secondary causes of hepatic steatosis (e.g., drug-induced liver injury, genetic liver disorders).

Sampling Technique: Sample was collected by random sampling technique.

DATA ANALYSIS PROCEDURE

Data were analyzed using SPSS, where descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, and percentages) were calculated for demographic and clinical variables. NAFLD grades were compared with serum ferritin levels, and Spearman’s rank correlation test was applied to assess the strength of association between ferritin and disease severity. Graphs and frequency tables were generated to display grade distribution and ferritin trends, and statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. This analysis helped determine how strongly serum ferritin correlates with NAFLD severity.

RESULTS:

Demographic data analysis

A total of 130 participants was include in my study and the mean age of the participants was 46.16 ± 9.33 years that shows that tha most of the patients were in the middle age category . the minmum record age of 23 year while maximum age was 70 years.

	Participants	Minimum	Maximum	Mean
Age of patient	130	23.00	70.00	46.1615±9.33

TABLE 1; Demographic characteristics of study participants age

Figure 1; Age distribution graph of participant (n=130)

Gender of patients

Out of 130 patients about 73 (56.2%) was male and other 57(43.8%) were female the gender distribution of participants is shown in figure 2

gender of patient			
	Gender	Frequency	Percent
	male	73	56.2
	female	57	43.8
	Total	130	100.0

Table 2; frequency table for gender of participants

Figure 2 ; Demographic chart of gender of participant

GRADE DISTRIBUTION

The distribution of NAFLD grades among the 130 participants is shown in table 3 out of the total participants 42 (32.3%) are in grade 1 and 55(42.3) are in grade 2 and 33(25.4%) are in grade 3 NAFLD. The result indicate that majority of participant had moderate NAFLD

The frequency distribution of the patient with NAFLD is illustrated in figure 3 which clearly show the proportion of participant in severity catogary . this descriptive analysis provides how severity in the study population is divided and serves as a basis for further comparison with ferritin

TABLE 3; DISTRIBUTION OF NAFLD GRADES IN 130 PARTICPANT

GRADE		Frequency	Percent
GRADE 1		42	32.3
GRADE 2		55	42.3
GRADE 3		33	25.4
Total		130	100.0

FIGURE 3; DISTRIBUTION OF NAFLD GRADES IN 130 PARTICPANT

Correlation of serum ferritin with different grade of NAFLD

A spearman’s rank correlation was applied to determine the serum ferritin correlation with grade of NAFLD. NAFLD is divide into 3 grades. The grade 1 is for mild and grade 2 is for moderate while grade 3 is for severe steatosis the analysis shows a

very Stronge positive correlation between ferritin and NAFLD ($r_s+0.935$, $p<0.001$, $n=130$), indicating that serum ferritin level increase significantly higher grades of NAFLD

The result showed a very stronge relation it indicate that serum ferritin levels increase progressively with higher NAFLD grade

Correlations

Spearman's rho		SERUM FERRITIN	Correlation Coefficient	SERUM FERRITIN	GRADE
				1.000	.935**
GRAD E	Correlation Coefficient	.935**	1.000		

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 :correlation of serum ferritin level and NAFLD patient(spearman’s rank correlation)

Figure 4 graphic representation of serum ferritin with grades of NAFLD

DISCUSSION

It was inferred from our findings that serum ferritin levels showed a very strong positive correlation with NAFLD severity grades ($r_s = 0.935, p < 0.001$), with mean ferritin values increasing progressively from 216.24 ng/mL in Grade 1 to 294.49 ng/mL in Grade 2 and finally to 396.00 ng/mL in Grade 3. Similarly, previous studies on NAFLD patients, such as Kowdley et al. (2012), reported elevated serum ferritin levels associated with advanced hepatic fibrosis and NASH, which were attributed to hepatic iron accumulation and systemic inflammation causing progressive liver injury. Consistent with those studies, the present research also provides strong evidence of increasing serum ferritin levels with higher NAFLD grades,

indicating that iron storage and dysregulated iron metabolism may contribute significantly to liver dysfunction and disease progression. It is well understood that elevated serum ferritin reflects both increased iron accumulation in hepatocytes and systemic inflammation, which may further exacerbate hepatocellular injury, oxidative stress, and progression to advanced fibrosis.

In this study, Grade 2 NAFLD was most common (42.3%), followed by Grade 1 (32.3%) and Grade 3/NASH (25.4%), indicating a high burden of moderate to advanced disease. Serum ferritin levels increased steadily with severity, rising from 216.24 ng/mL in Grade 1 to 294.49 ng/mL in Grade 2 and 396.00 ng/mL in Grade 3 an 83% increase from

simple steatosis to NASH, closely matching the 84.5% rise reported by Duseja et al. (2015). Despite higher absolute ferritin levels in our urban Pakistani cohort compared to Indian patients, the proportional increase remained consistent, suggesting population differences in diet, genetics, and inflammation. Our correlation coefficient ($r_s = 0.935$) was markedly stronger than those reported in Western studies (0.60–0.75) and stronger than associations noted by Buzzetti et al. (2019), highlighting serum ferritin as a highly reliable non-invasive biomarker for assessing NAFLD severity and monitoring disease progression in Pakistani patients.

Overall, these results confirm that serum ferritin levels are strongly affected by NAFLD severity, with a correlation coefficient of 0.935 representing one of the strongest relationships reported in the literature. The progressive increase in mean ferritin from 216.24 ng/mL in Grade 1 to 396.00 ng/mL in Grade 3 demonstrates a clear dose-response relationship between iron metabolism dysregulation and disease severity. These findings validate serum ferritin as a valuable non-invasive biomarker for assessing NAFLD severity in Pakistani patients and provide a strong rationale for incorporating ferritin measurement into routine clinical assessment. Monitoring serum ferritin levels, along with lifestyle interventions including weight reduction, dietary modifications to reduce iron and calorie intake, increased physical activity, and early management of metabolic risk factors including diabetes and obesity, is recommended to prevent disease progression. Future research should explore whether serial ferritin measurements can predict long-term clinical outcomes such as progression to cirrhosis or hepatocellular carcinoma, whether interventions targeting iron metabolism can slow NAFLD progression, and whether the ferritin-NAFLD relationship differs across demographic subgroups to improve patient care and treatment strategies in NAFLD management.

CONCLUSION(S)

The present study investigated the relationship between NAFLD severity, liver enzymes (ALT, AST, ALP), and serum ferritin levels. The findings indicate that serum ferritin levels tend to increase with higher NAFLD grades, suggesting that iron accumulation may contribute to hepatic stress. Although the

correlation between liver enzymes and serum ferritin was generally weak, it indicates that other metabolic or clinical factors also influence liver function in NAFLD patients.

The analysis of demographic variables revealed that NAFLD was more prevalent among males and adults in the middle-age group, highlighting the influence of gender and age on disease prevalence. Grade 2 NAFLD was the most common among the study population, while Grade 3 had the lowest number of patients. Overall, these findings provide evidence that iron storage, metabolic factors, and liver enzyme variations are interconnected, though liver dysfunction in NAFLD is multifactorial.

Therefore, regular monitoring of liver enzymes and serum ferritin is important to assess disease progression and prevent further hepatic complications. Early diagnosis, lifestyle interventions, and management of metabolic risk factors can improve patient outcomes. Further research with larger sample sizes, long-term follow-up, and advanced diagnostic methods is recommended to enhance understanding of NAFLD-related liver dysfunction.

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